

Complex Compounds of 2-Aminobenzothiazole with Cu (II), Co (II) and Hg (II)

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The metal complexes of 2-aminobenzothiazole (I) have not been investigated though its complexes with Ag and Hg are known¹. Since four membered chelate rings are known to be formed by alkylxanthates^{2,3}, dialkyldithiocarbamates⁴ and 2-mercaptobenzothiazole^{5,6}, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the interaction of 2-aminobenzothiazole with metal ions.

In the present note it is shown that 2-aminobenzothiazole reacts with Cu(II), Co(II) and Hg(II) in dil. HCl and acetic acid medium separately in presence of sodium acetate to give metallic complexes of the type $M(C_7H_6N_2S)_x$ where x = chloride or acetate.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-aminobenzothiazole (I) was prepared by Hugershoff's method¹. The compound was recrystallised from dil. ethanol and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ under vacuum (m.p. 122°).

Preparation of Cu(II) and Hg(II) Complexes : 50 ml of 0.1 M solution of 2-aminobenzothiazole in dil. HCl were added to 20 ml. of 0.1 M metal salts ($CuCl_2$, $CoCl_2$, $HgCl_2$) solution. The mixture was heated for 20 min. and then followed by addition of saturated solution of sodium acetate till the precipitation was complete. The coloured precipitate was allowed to settle and then filtered. It was washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The metal complexes were analysed for metal, sulphur, carbon and hydrogen (Table 1).

1. A. Hugershoff, *Ber*, 1903, **36**, 3134.
2. L. Malatesta, *Gazzetta*, 1940, **70**, 541, 553.
3. L. Cambi and L. Szego, (i) *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2591; (ii) *Ber.*, 1933, **66**, 656.
4. L. Malatesta and R. Pizzotti, *Chemical Industria*, 1945, **27**, 6.
5. M. Kuras, *Chem. Obzor.*, 1939, **14**, 145.
6. J. V. Dubsky, *Mikrochemie*, 1940, **28**, 145, (*C.A.*, 1940, **34**, 4686).

However, if acetic acid was the medium of reaction, it was observed that in all the cases complexes of the type $M(C_7H_6N_2S)x_2$ (where x = acetate) were obtained although initially metal chlorides ($CuCl_2$, $CoCl_2$ and $Hg(NO_3)_2$) were used. This was confirmed by preparing the above complexes through the interaction of 2-aminobenzothiazole and metal acetates (Table 2).

TABLE 1

		%M	%S	%C	%H
Cu complex	Found	21.91	11.01	29.10	2.00
	Required for	22.31	11.25	29.52	2.11
	$Cu(C_7H_6N_2S)Cl_2$				
Co complex	Found	20.88	10.44	27.81	1.96
	Required for	21.06	10.67	28.01	2.001
	$Co(C_7H_6N_2S)Cl_2$				
Hg complex	Found	47.80	6.91	19.30	1.21
	Required for	47.57	7.59	19.90	1.40
	$Hg(C_7H_6N_2S)Cl_2$				

TABLE 2

		%M	%S	%C	%H
Cu complex	Found	19.01	9.71	39.61	3.51
	Required for	19.15	9.66	39.88	3.62
	$Cu(C_7H_6N_2S)x_2^*$				
Co complex	Found	17.81	9.25	40.51	3.48
	Required for	18.03	9.77	40.30	3.60
	$Co(C_7H_6N_2S)x_2$				
Hg complex	Found	42.10	6.51	27.91	2.33
	Required for	42.80	6.82	28.16	2.56
	$Hg(C_7H_6N_2S)x_2$				

* where x = acetate in all the cases.

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